

Polychelates of 4,4'-bis[(*N*-phenylsalicylaldimine-5)azo]biphenyl with some transition metal ions

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4,4'-Bis[*N*-phenylsalicylaldimine-5)azo]biphenyl and its polychelates with Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III}, Ti^{III}, VO^{II}, Zr^{IV}, Th^{IV} and UO₂^{II} have been prepared. The ligand acts as bisbidentate molecule coordinating through phenolic O and azomethine N atoms. The thermal data have been analyzed. The d.c. electrical conductivity data reveal semiconducting nature of the polychelates. All the polychelates and ligand have been screened for their antimicrobial activity.

The azo compounds gained much attention because of their use as models of biological systems^{1,2}. Literature survey reveals that most of the work has been done on the bivalent transition metal complexes of Schiff bases³, but scanty work is reported on azodye transition metal polychelates having different oxidation states. Hence it was considered of interest to synthesize bis-bidentate Schiff base ligand having azodye group which can form polychelates with transition metal ions with various oxidation states. The Schiff base ligand 4,4'-bis[(*N*-phenylsalicylaldimine-5)azo]biphenyl (BPSAB) has been synthesized from 4,4'-bis[(salicylaldehyde-5)azo]biphenyl and aniline. The polychelates of BPSAB with Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III}, Ti^{III}, VO^{II}, Zr^{IV}, Th^{IV} and UO₂^{II} have been synthesized and characterized by various physicochemical methods.

Results and Discussion

All the dark brown coloured polychelates are insoluble in water and common organic solvents, which indicates their polymeric nature^{4,5}. Elemental analysis suggests 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry.

IR spectrum of the ligand shows a strong band at 3050 cm⁻¹ due to intramolecular hydrogen bonded phenolic OH stretching^{4,6}. It disappears in the spectra of polychelates, suggesting deprotonation of OH and coordination of oxygen with the metal ions, which is also confirmed by the positive shift (25–57 cm⁻¹) of the ligand band at 1250 cm⁻¹ due to phenolic C–O stretch^{2,7}. The strong band at 1610 cm⁻¹ (C=N) shows a negative shift of 10–20 cm⁻¹ in the polychelates, indicating the participation of azomethine nitrogen in chelate formation. New bands observed at 490–540 and 400–475 cm⁻¹ in all polychelates may be assigned to ν M–O and ν M–N modes, respectively⁸. This also confirms coordination through deprotonated phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen. The bands at 3350–3450 cm⁻¹ in

the spectra of polychelates may be due to OH vibrations of water molecules. Polychelates also exhibit sharp peaks at 820–840 cm⁻¹ assignable to the presence of coordinated water molecules. The polychelate shows a band at 970 cm⁻¹ (V=O) which is characteristic of V^{IV}-oxo compounds⁹. The diagnostic ν O=U=O stretching mode is observed at 920 cm⁻¹ in the UO₂^{II} polychelate^{2,10}.

The electronic spectrum of the Cr^{III} polychelate shows three bands at 16835, 21550 and 27780 cm⁻¹ assignable to ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4B_{2g}$ and ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ transitions, respectively, suggesting octahedral geometry around Cr^{III} ion¹¹. Its magnetic moment (3.94 B.M.) shows the presence of three unpaired electrons. The magnetic moment of the Fe^{III} polychelate is 6.15 B.M. and its electronic spectrum displays three bands at 11365, 21190 and 25250 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$ transitions, respectively. Hence it is evident that the complex possesses high-spin octahedral configuration¹¹. The Mn^{III} chelate has magnetic moment of 4.86 B.M. and its electronic spectrum exhibits three bands at 13500, 16550 and 18120 cm⁻¹ assignable to ${}^5B_1 \rightarrow {}^5B_2$, ${}^5B_1 \rightarrow {}^5A_1$ and ${}^5B_1 \rightarrow {}^5E$ transitions, respectively, suggesting square-pyramidal geometry around Mn^{III} ion¹². The magnetic moment for the Ti^{III} polychelate is 1.64 B.M., corresponding to one unpaired electron. The Ti^{III} polychelate exhibits a band at 18180 cm⁻¹ attributed to the transition ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, suggesting octahedral geometry¹³. The oxovanadium polychelate has magnetic moment of 1.94 B.M. and its electronic spectrum displays three bands at 10920, 19600 and 26300 cm⁻¹, assigned to $b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow c^*$ ($d_{xy} d_{yz}$), $b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow b_1^*(d_{x^2-y^2})$ and $b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow a_1^*(d_{z^2})$ transitions, respectively, suggesting octahedral geometry¹⁴. The polychelates of Zr^{IV}, Th^{IV} and UO₂^{II} are diamagnetic as expected and their electronic spectra do not furnish any relevant information.

The d.c. electrical conductivity of the ligand and its polychelates in their pellet form was studied over a temperature range 313–493 K. The general behavior of electrical conductivity obeys the relation, $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/kT)$, where σ_0 is a constant, E_a the activation energy of conduction process, T the absolute temperature and k the Boltzman constant. The room temperature electrical conductivity lies in the range 1.35×10^{-9} to $2.91 \times 10^{-11} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, indicating their semiconducting nature¹². A linear relationship between $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ has been observed. All plots show two distinct regions. In the low temperature region, the slopes of the plots have small values. This may be due to extrinsic conduction present in them, whereas in the high temperature region, a linear dependence with high value of $\log \sigma = F(10^3/T)$ was observed. In this temperature domain these polychelates may behave as intrinsic semiconductors^{4,16,15,16}. This behavior can be attributed to interaction between the electrons of *d*-orbitals and the σ -orbitals of the ligand at upper temperature range. This interaction will lead to localized action of σ -electronic charge on the ligand which tends to increase the activation energy¹⁵. A higher value of electrical conductivity of ligand may be attributed to the presence of a large number of σ and lone-pairs of electrons in conjugation, the mobility of which increases at higher temperatures. At 493 K, the electrical conductivity of polychelates increases in the order : BPSAB > Fe > Ti > Mn > Zr > VO > Cr > UO₂ > Th. The activation energy of electrical conduction lies in the range 0.285–0.929 eV.

The thermogravimetric analysis shows that the decomposition of polychelates takes place in two steps in the temperature range 40–700°. The initial weight-loss (*ca.* 5%) upto 230°, corresponds to the presence of two coordinated water molecules in the Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Th^{IV} and Ti^{III} polychelates¹⁷, while in the VO^{II} polychelate one coordinated water molecule is present. In the case of the Mn^{III} and UO₂^{II} polychelates, negligible weight-loss has been observed upto 220°, indicating absence of any water molecule. After the elimination of water molecules in first step, all the polychelates are found to be stable for a short while upto *ca.* 300°, but above this they show continuous mass-loss upto 700°. This mass-loss may be due to oxidative degradation of chelates leading to formation of metal oxide¹⁶. From the procedural decomposition temperature, the thermal stability order of polychelates is found to be : Ti > UO₂ > Th > Cr > VO > Zr > Mn > Fe. The Broido's plots of $\ln[\ln(1/y)]$ vs $1/T$ are found to be straight-lines corresponding to first order decomposition reaction. The slopes of plots yield the thermal activation energy of decomposition of polychelates which lies between 12.22 and 82.63 kJ mol⁻¹.

The ligand and its polychelates were screened for their antimicrobial activity against *S aureus*, *E coli*, *S typhi* and *Ps aeruginosa* by disc-diffusion method¹⁸. Compared with the control (DMSO) the ligand shows good activity against all microorganisms (zone of inhibition 8–11 mm) except *E coli*, which is resistant. The polychelate of Mn^{III}

Table 1 Analytical and physical data of polychelates

Compd	Metal % Found (Calcd)	μ_{eff} B M	Decomp temp °C	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	Elec cond $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	E_a eV
BPSAB	–	Diamag	250*	37.54	3.01×10^{-10a} 6.36×10^{-8b}	0.929
[Cr BPSAB 2H ₂ O] _n	7.48 (7.58)	3.94	328	82.63	2.91×10^{-11a} 4.61×10^{-9b}	0.543
[Mn BPSAB OAc] _n	7.67 (7.72)	4.86	295	65.65	3.21×10^{-11a} 2.33×10^{-8b}	0.466
[Fe BPSAB 2H ₂ O] _n	8.00 (8.10)	6.15	285	54.01	1.35×10^{-9a} 5.77×10^{-8b}	0.601
[VO BPSAB H ₂ O] _n	7.35 (7.46)	1.93	318	50.15	1.02×10^{-9a} 1.61×10^{-8b}	0.778
[Zr BPSAB 2H ₂ O] _n	12.42 (12.58)	Diamag	315	12.22	3.48×10^{-10a} 1.63×10^{-8b}	0.406
[Th BPSAB 2H ₂ O] _n	26.60 (26.79)	Diamag	330	45.93	3.41×10^{-11a} 8.92×10^{-10b}	0.539
[Ti BPSAB 2H ₂ O] _n	7.00 (7.02)	1.64	395	52.22	5.73×10^{-10a} 5.35×10^{-8b}	0.285
[UO ₂ BPSAB] _n	27.30 (27.42)	Diamag	348	44.68	3.47×10^{-11a} 2.77×10^{-9b}	0.531

*M_p (°C) ^aAt 313 K ^bAt 493 K

could only inhibit the growth of *S. aureus* (10 mm), and the other species are resistant to it. The polychelate of Cr^{III} shows good activity against *S. aureus* (9 mm) and *S. typhi* (10 mm). The polychelates of Fe^{III} and Th^{IV} could inhibit the growth of all microorganisms to a greater extent (zone of inhibition 10–11 mm), whereas the other polychelates show moderate activity against the microorganisms. In general, it can be concluded that after the formation of coordination polychelates, the activity against the microorganisms increases considerably.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solvents were used after distillation¹⁹.

The Schiff base : The dye 4,4'-bis[(salicylaldehyde-5-azo]biphenyl was prepared by reported method²⁰. A 1 : 2 mixture of the dye (0.005 mol in 25 ml methanol) and aniline (0.01 mol in 25 ml ethanol) was refluxed on a water-bath in the presence of a drop of conc. H₂SO₄ for 3 h. 4,4'-Bis[(*N*-phenylsalicylaldehyde-5-azo]biphenyl (BPSAB) was obtained as a dark brown solid which was crystallized from DMF-ethanol mixture, (70%), m.p. 250°.

The polychelates : To a solution of the ligand (0.005 mol) dissolved in DMF (25 ml), solution of the metal salt (0.005 mol; CrCl₃.6H₂O, Mn(OAc)₃.2H₂O, FeCl₃, VOSO₄.5H₂O, ZrOCl₂.8H₂O, Th(NO₃)₄.5H₂O, TiCl₃ and UO₂(NO₃)₂.6H₂O) in ethanol (25 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. The mixture was refluxed on an oil-bath for 2–3 h. The resulting dark brown coloured polychelates were washed with hot water, DMF, ethanol and finally with acetone, and dried in air at room temperature.

Elemental analyses were carried out at Microanalytical Laboratory, R.S.I.C., Punjab University, Chandigarh. The metal contents were determined by reported method²¹. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as the calibrant and calculations were made using computed values of Pascal's constants. The electronic spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss DMR-21 spectrophotometer at I.I.T., Chennai and IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 842 spectrophotometer. TG analysis was carried in air atmosphere at a heating rate of 10°/min. The d.c. electrical conductivity was measured in the pellet form using d.c. microvoltmeter.

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References

1. S. G. Bhadange, R. B. Mohod and A. S. Aswar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1110; D. S. Raj, *Res. J. Chem. Environ.*, 2001, **5**, 35.
2. A. F. Shoair, A. A. El-Bindary, A. Z. El-Sonbati and R. M. Younes, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 2000, **74**, 1047.
3. P. P. Hankare, R. K. Patil, S. S. Chavan, A. H. Jagtap and P. S. Battase, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1326; A. P. Mishra and M. K. Khare, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 367; S. G. Swamy and S. R. Reddy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1093.
4. P. J. Bahad, N. S. Bhavne and A. S. Aswar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 363.
5. D. J. Sutariya, J. R. Patel and M. N. Patel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 309.
6. A. S. Aswar and N. S. Bhavne, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 75.
7. B. Pancholi and M. M. Patel, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 1996, **13**, 261.
8. K. Nakamoto and C. W. Schaapfer, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1972, **6**, 17.
9. A. S. Ceccato, A. Neves, M. A. de Brito, S. M. Drechsel, A. S. Mangrich, R. Werner, W. Hasse and A. J. Brotholuzzi, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2000, 1573.
10. M. T. H. Tarafder and A. K. Khan, *Polyhedron*, 1991, **10**, 819.
11. P. K. Rai and R. N. Prasad, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organ. Chem.*, 1994, **24**, 749; R. Saraswat and V. B. Rana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 493.
12. R. Mukhopadhyay, S. Bhattacharjee and R. Bhattacharya, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1994, 2799.
13. M. S. Islam and M. A. Alam, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 255.
14. A. M. Karampurwala, A. Ray and P. R. Patel, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organ. Chem.*, 1989, **19**, 219.
15. K. A. El-Manakhly, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 315.
16. A. S. Aswar, R. G. Mahale, P. R. Kakde and S. G. Bhadange, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 395.
17. A. S. Aswar and N. S. Bhavne, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1990, **157**, 23.
18. R. Anathanarayan and C. K. J. Panikar, "Text Book of Microbiology", 5th. ed., Orient Longman Ltd., Hyderabad, 1996.
19. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Qualitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, London, 1961.
20. A. K. Rana, N. R. Shaha, M. S. Patil, A. M. Karampurwala and J. R. Shah, *Macromol. Chem.*, 1981, **182**, 3387.
21. A. S. Aswar, P. J. Bahad, A. V. Pardhi and N. S. Bhavne, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 1988, **5**, 233.